

**SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH WORKS ABOUT POPULATION CENSUS
(in the case of Uzbekistan).**

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Abstract: In all countries of the world, statistical data on the population, human factor and solving social problems are of great importance for the social and economic development of each country. Also, today, many countries of the world have laws on statistics, which stipulate that the data obtained from individuals during the population registration should be used only for statistical purposes, and the owner should be announced in an abstracted form.

Key words: society, holding democratic elections, rational use of state resources, distribution.

In the world, scientific research is being carried out in such areas as population census processes, the procedures and methods of their organization and conducting, the history of these events, the impact of the population census process on the demographic situation, and the characteristics of the census processes. Also, by regularly conducting population censuses in the countries of the world, solving the human factor and its social problems, studying ethnodemographic processes, obtaining accurate information about migration and emigration, and the dynamics of the population, as well as developing appropriate state-addressed action programs, special importance is attached to regular conducting of population census every 5 years. In particular, we would like to briefly dwell on the scientific researches and their periodization related to the conduct of these population census activities in the territory of our country.

From the end of the 19th century to the first half of the 20th century, the literature published on the population census conducted in the territory of present-

day Uzbekistan and the research works on the subject can be divided into four groups in terms of periodical and methodological approach: the first - literature created during the Russian Empire; the second - research carried out during the Soviet period; the third - works published during the years of independence; the fourth is works created by foreign authors.

In the first group: a number of works, statistical collections[1] created in connection with the population census activities[2] at the end of the 19th century and the first quarter of the 20th century have a special place. In these publications and statistical collections, in addition to the conduct of the population census, its goals and tasks, there is a lot of information and statistical figures on the final results of the first event held in Turkestan in 1897.

The second group includes: literature created in the first years of the establishment of Soviet power[3], statistical collections on the subject, a number of literature published by economists[4], geographers, demographers during the 60-80s of the 20th century, and works created by historians. Through these scientific research works, it is possible to have a certain idea about the population census[5] activities conducted in the regions[6] during this period. In particular, issues such as the growth of the population in the regions, the number of births, deaths, migration and population differences in the regions, as well as the national structure of the population, are given special importance.

In the third group: literature covering one or another aspect of the census activities of the years of independence, researches on the subject were included. Some issues related to the socio-economic aspect of the researched problem were partially covered in the scientific research carried out during the years of independence. In the research conducted during this period, the dynamics of population growth, the history of demography, migration, the daily lifestyle of the population, and employment of the population were more emphasized.

The fourth group includes research conducted in foreign countries, including research conducted in the Russian Federation, scientific research on the subject conducted in various countries of the United States and the European Union, and research works of Kazakh scientists, as well as a number of articles. They expressed their views on demography, history of demography, characteristics of migration, population employment, census methods, population dynamics, social problems of the population, and theoretical and modern directions of census activities.

During the development of society, censuses began very early, in particular, there are records of censuses in Egypt, Mesopotamia, India, and China in 2800, 2250, and 2238 BC [16]. It is also known that censuses were held in Greece and Rome in the IV century BC. In Japan and Babylon, censuses were also conducted from ancient times, and the main purpose of this process was to collect taxes from the population, collect various types of duties, and to know the number of the population (mainly men) was very important for military purposes.

In conclusion, it can be said that although some notable scientific publications and research results have been published within the framework of the topic, the statistical collections of the final results of the population census activities and archival data related to this process serve as the main source.

The study of population census activities conducted in the territory of Uzbekistan and the analytical scientific conclusions obtained from them will increase the interest of the growing young generation and readers interested in the history of these processes to study the history of these activities in depth. For this reason, studying the history of census activities serves to properly organize such activities that are held today.

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